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PERIODICAL PRESS AND CREATION OF ITS LEGAL BASIS

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Annotation: The article covers the periodical press and the fact that journalists of Uzbekistan, due to national independence, for the first time in their history, have achieved the legal and political basis necessary for democratic development. This basis is also an important guarantee for the development of journalism in a free society. The adoption of mass media laws is concrete. It is a phenomenon caused by the current social and political processes in our country, and it is a sign that different opinions and views are developing in our country and that democratic values have taken a strong place in the social life of Uzbekistan.

Keywords: Press, mass media, law, legal, court, authority, guarantee, freedom, system, independence, activity

Since independence, the journalism of our country has become a vital necessity to operate within the framework of relevant laws in the legal space, and first of all, it should serve the interests of the people. After all, the place of mass media in a democratic legal society is determined not by the government, but by the audience and readership. Therefore, the problem of forming free mass media in our republic, strengthening their legal base in accordance with world standards and democratic requirements nowadays has become an urgent issue.

According to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, June 27th – the date of establishment of the “Taraqqi” newspaper, was declared “Day of press and mass media employees”¹ in our country. In the conditions of independence, one of the most important changes in the time press system of the republic is the creation of special newspapers in the languages of other people living in the republic, such as Russians, Kazakhs, and Turkmens, along with the increase of publications in the Uzbek language. 153 newspapers and magazines are published in different languages in our country, among them there are editions published in two, three and even four languages². The

¹Since 1997, June 27 has been celebrated as Mass Media Day in our country.

²Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “About mass media”, December 26, 1997. “On amendments and additions to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “About mass media”. “Khalk suzi”, January 16, 2007.

declaration of mass media of the Republic of Uzbekistan as free and the adoption of the special law “About mass media” was an important political and cultural event³. The legal status of mass media, the place, role, main tasks and activities of journalism in the political system of the State and society in general began to change. As a part of the history of the republic, a new system of the press, which operates in the conditions of a humane legal democratic state, was established. However, in the early days of independence, under the influence of a number of objective and subjective factors, the development process of the press became more complicated. Because of the change in the press culture, journalists have been able to provide the public with unbiased information. The experience gained in the years of independence in creating a new system of the press, the characteristics of the press in the market conditions, including the problems of increasing the economic efficiency of editorial activities, still require important scientific-theoretical, practical analysis and research. The press, in general, the current and future successful development of mass media depends on finding the right solutions to these problems.

In general, it is desirable to have the following four important legal bases for journalism to become a real “fourth power”:

- democratic and solid constitutional guarantee and its implementation;
- democratic laws and legal norms (including the legal guarantee of economic freedom of mass media) and their practical activities;
- the conditions of political freedom, that is, the study of the intervention of the state power in the work of mass media and their right to criticize the government;
- the last but important foundation - independent judiciary⁴.

Social and political stability in the country is sufficiently dependent on the state of public opinion, and another social institution - the mass media - was given an important role in its formation.

From this point of view, we have both the duty and the right to note the great role of the Uzbek press in the revival of the historical, advanced traditions and values of our people, the rich spiritual life of our ancient country, and the unique contribution to the current global and regional traditions. In this sense, it

² Abduazimova N. History of national journalism. (Era of national independence). In two volumes. Vol. 2. Tashkent: Shark. 2008. -p 238.

³ Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “About mass media”, December 26, 1997.
(The new version of the “Law on measures to support mass media” was adopted on June 27, 2022).

⁴ Abduazimova N. History of national journalism. (Era of national independence). In two volumes. Vol. 2. Tashkent: Shark. 2008. -p 329.

is appropriate to interpret the history of the press of Uzbekistan as a phenomenon interrelated with the history of science, the history of thought and the history of enlightenment. Therefore, the role of journalism as the “fourth power” in society is determined by the age, quality, experience and level of development of democracy.

Therefore, the constitutional norms and laws related to the mass media are the main factors of the effectiveness of journalism. At present, we have the opportunity to receive direct information about the events taking place in different parts of the world. And there is no doubt that in the future this process will expand further, acquire new meaning, and the press and information media will become more liberalized.

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